

AI-Enhanced Tools for the Forensic Chemical Analysis of Illicit Drugs, Cannabis, and NPS in Southeast Asia: A Scoping Review with Proposed Roadmap

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Abstract

This scoping review maps the current landscape of artificial intelligence (AI)-enhanced tools supporting forensic chemical analysis of illicit drugs, Cannabis, and new psychoactive substances (NPS) in Southeast Asia (SEA). Using the PRISMA-ScR framework, we systematically searched 8 databases, identifying 12 relevant studies that met inclusion criteria of AI application in forensic chemistry with SEA authorship. The selected studies span a variety of AI methods—including machine learning, deep learning, and ensemble models—applied to data from spectroscopy, imaging, sensor arrays, and GC-MS platforms. These tools demonstrated strong potential in improving speed, accuracy, and nondestructive testing capabilities for substance classification and quantification. However, challenges such as limited diversity and standardization of datasets, potential overfitting, inconsistent validation protocols, and constraints in cross-laboratory reproducibility remain. Our findings highlight the promise and current limitations of AI integration in forensic laboratories across the region. This review concludes by outlining a roadmap for leveraging AI to advance forensic chemical analysis in SEA while addressing existing limitations and future opportunities.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, machine learning, deep learning, prompt engineering, forensic chemistry, illicit drug, new psychoactive substance, Southeast Asia, chemometric

1. Introduction

Forensic chemical analysis is the application of chemical methodologies to detect, identify, and quantify substances within the legal context [1]. Forensic chemists (FCs) play a critical role in combating the global illicit drug trade. Apart from common illicit substances such as methamphetamine and Cannabis, the emergence of new psychoactive substances (NPS), often designed to circumvent existing drug laws, presents a significant and ongoing challenge to forensic laboratories [2]. Artificial intelligence (AI) offers a transformative approach to enhance the speed, accuracy, and efficiency of forensic drug analysis [3]. This review focuses on AI tools studied and used in Southeast Asia (SEA), a region facing significant challenges related to illicit drug trafficking and abuse [4]. These tools may have the potential to assist FCs in their analyses.

The economic limitations of most SEA countries often hinder FCs from accessing the advanced computer-related learning systems available in developed nations. Consequently, foundational AI concepts may not be widely integrated into forensic training. For the purposes of this review, we define AI as a field of computer science that enables machines to perform tasks typically requiring human intelligence. AI forms include the following:

- **Machine learning (ML):** Algorithms that allow computers to learn from data without explicit programming. This can involve training models to classify drugs, identify unknown compounds, or predict their properties. Common ML techniques include support vector machines (SVMs), random forests (RFs), and k-nearest neighbors [5].
- **Deep learning (DL):** DL is a subset of ML that uses artificial neural networks with multiple layers (deep neural networks) to analyze complex data. DL models can process hyperspectral imaging and mass spectrometry (MS) data [4], as well as enhance sensory analysis for E-nose, E-tongue, and E-eye [6].

- **Natural language processing (NLP):** This enables computers to understand and process human language. NLP can assist FCs without a coding background by generating scripts and automating workflows. The effectiveness of NLP models often depends on prompt engineering, which involves crafting precise inputs to maximize AI-generated outputs. By optimizing prompts, forensic analysts can enhance data-extraction accuracy and generate more relevant insights from large textual datasets [5].
- **Expert Systems:** These are computer programs designed to mimic the decision-making abilities of a human expert. FCs can apply them in automated spectral interpretation, i.e., analyzing and interpreting NMR, IR, or MS data by comparing unknown substances with vast forensic databases [5].

Figure 1 illustrates the key branches of AI as aforementioned. Other forms of AI include speech processing for text-to-speech and speech-to-text conversion, vision AI for image recognition and machine vision, planning and optimization for problem-solving strategies, and robotics for automated tasks [4].

Figure 1: Overview of AI forms with practical application in forensic chemistry

Notably, AI goes beyond traditional chemometrics by its ability to learn from data in a more autonomous and flexible manner. AI can identify nonlinear relationships, automatically extract relevant features, and handle high-dimensional data, making it particularly well suited for the complexities of modern forensic analysis [7].

AI tools can assist FCs by automating their repetitive and time-consuming tasks, allowing them to focus on more complex and critical aspects of their work. One of its most significant contributions is in data preprocessing, where AI streamlines baseline correction, noise reduction, and peak alignment in spectroscopic data, minimizing manual effort. It also plays a crucial role in preliminary screening, rapidly analyzing large datasets—such as those from GC-MS—to flag potential samples of interest for further examination. Beyond speed, AI enhances pattern recognition, identifying subtle variations in spectra that may indicate the presence of specific drugs or adulterants, patterns that could otherwise go unnoticed by human analysts [8]. With the use of sensory analysis tools such as E-nose, E-tongue, and E-eye for chemical screening, forensic laboratories can also reduce their operational costs [9].

To explore the role of AI in forensic chemical analysis within SEA, we conducted a comprehensive scoping review following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) framework. Compared with a systematic review, a scoping review aims to scope a body of literature, identify knowledge gaps, or to inform a future systematic review [10]. This review maps the current body of research involving AI-enhanced tools for analyzing illicit drugs, Cannabis, and new psychoactive substances (NPS) across the region. A strategic roadmap is also outlined to support the integration of AI in forensic workflows and promote the modernization of SEA forensic laboratories.

2. Methods

2.1 Protocol and Registration

This scoping review is guided by the PRISMA-ScR framework [11]. A formal protocol for this review has not been registered.

2.1.1 Research Questions (RQs)

RQ1: What AI, ML, or DL methods have been applied to the forensic chemical analysis of illicit drugs, Cannabis, and NPS by researchers affiliated with Southeast Asian institutions?

RQ2: What chemical analysis techniques (e.g., spectroscopy, chromatography, sensor arrays, etc.) are most commonly integrated with AI tools in the identified studies?

RQ3: What forensic applications or outcomes such as substance classification, quantification, or real-time detection have been achieved through these AI-enhanced methods?

RQ4: What thematic trends, methodological gaps, or research clusters emerge from the current literature, and how can these assist FCs' work and AI integration in SEA?

2.2 Eligibility Criteria

Studies were included in this review based on the following criteria:

- ✓ Research articles that applied AI tools to forensic chemical analysis.
- ✓ Studies demonstrating applications relevant to the classification, and description of illicit drugs, cannabis, and NPS.
- ✓ Application of AI in recognized techniques.
- ✓ At least one author must be affiliated with an institution based in SEA.

Exclusion criteria included the following:

- ✗ Studies focusing on medical, enforcement, or sociocultural aspects of drug use (without direct application to chemical analysis).
- ✗ Studies using mathematical or geometrical techniques without explicit AI methodologies.
- ✗ Review articles that do not present original research using AI tools (unless they specifically address the potential of AI in a way relevant to the RQs).
- ✗ Studies not related to the analysis of illicit drugs, Cannabis, or NPS.
- ✗ Studies where no author is affiliated with a SEA institution.

2.3 Information Sources

A structured Boolean search was conducted across eight databases, namely, PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, CORE.ac.uk, ResearchGate, and Springer. Searches were conducted in March and April 2025 without date limitations. The final search yielded 612 records, with 43 duplicates removed. This left 569 titles and abstracts for screening. After applying inclusion and exclusion criteria, 12 studies were included in the final synthesis.

The following search syntax was adapted for each database except ScienceDirect: (("artificial intelligence" OR "large language" OR "natural language" OR "machine learning" OR "deep learning") AND ("methamphetamine" OR "ketamine" OR "cocaine" OR "ecstasy" OR "controlled substance" OR "controlled drug" OR "forensic chemistry" OR "illicit drug" OR "clandestine laboratory" OR "cannabis" OR "psychoactive" OR "narcotic")) AND ("Brunei" OR "Cambodia" OR "Indonesia" OR "Laos" OR "Malaysia" OR "Myanmar" OR "Philippines" OR "Singapore" OR "Thailand" OR "Vietnam" OR "Southeast Asia"). For ScienceDirect, the above syntax was modified into separate search queries because the maximum number of Boolean connectors is eight per field.

2.4 Selection of Sources of Evidence

Two reviewers independently screened titles and abstracts to identify studies for inclusion. Discrepancies were resolved through discussion. Twelve full-text articles were reviewed, with no exclusions at this stage. A PRISMA-ScR flow diagram was constructed accordingly, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: PRISMA-ScR flow diagram

2.5 Data-Charting Process

Data were extracted using a predefined charting form that was pilot tested prior to use. Extracted fields included the first author and year, country, AI tool/method, analytical technique, drug/s analyzed, how AI was leveraged, key findings, and limitations identified.

2.6 Synthesis of Results

The results were synthesized through a narrative approach, and the key findings are summarized in Table 1.

2.7 Critical Appraisal of Individual Sources

A critical appraisal of individual studies was also conducted, as shown in Table 2.

3. Results

A total of 12 studies met the inclusion criteria. These studies demonstrate the application of AI to various forensic tasks, including drug classification, compound quantification, GC-MS pattern recognition, and the development of portable detection tools. The AI tools range from conventional ML algorithms to DL and hybrid techniques. For each study, Table 1 summarizes the key findings, whereas Table 2 summarizes the results of critical appraisal. The detailed version of the critical appraisal is available as a Supplemental material upon reasonable request.

Table 1: Key findings of the included studies

First Author & Year	Country	AI Tool/ Method	Analytical Technique	Drug/s Analyzed	How AI Was Leveraged	Key Findings	Limitations Identified
Chang 2025 [12]	MY	K-nearest neighbor, logistic regression, support vector machine, decision tree, random forest	Attenuated Total Reflectance–Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR)	Methamphetamine, heroin, benzodiazepines	Classification of drug substances based on spectral data.	Random Forest model achieved 99.6% accuracy.	Lack of detailed information on sample selection, data collection parameters, and validation methods.
Yusof 2021 [13]	MY	Shallow one-dimensional convolutional neural network (1DCNN)	3D molecular descriptors	Amphetamine-type stimulants (ATS)	Classification of ATS drugs using molecular descriptors as input for the 1DCNN model.	1DCNN achieved comparable performance to Random Forest.	Details of the dataset of ATS drugs and the derivation of the 3D molecular descriptors are not fully clear. Validation methodology requires further scrutiny.
Rahmantyo 2019 [14]	ID	Support Vector Machine (SVM), Principal Component Analysis (PCA)	Electronic Tongue (TOMA and OA lipids)	Cannabis (pure, mixed with tea, mixed with tobacco)	Feature selection using PCA to optimize sensor array and SVM for classification.	Optimized sensor subsets (6 for cannabis-tea, 3 for cannabis-tobacco) achieved 100% accuracy with reduced running time.	Lack of detailed information on sample selection, exact validation procedure, and specific sensor array composition.
Aryati 2020 [15]	ID	Deep Learning (CNN), Machine Learning (Fingerprint Similarity-Based Clustering), Pharmacophore Modeling	2D NPS structures, Fingerprints, Physicochemical properties	Cannabinoid- and cathinone-derived compounds (New Psychoactive Substances - NPS)	Classification of NPS compounds using different AI methods and comparing their performance.	Deep learning method using fingerprints showed the best performance for classifying both types of compounds with high accuracy.	Selection criteria for the NPS database are not fully described. Detailed information on the validation methods for deep learning models is lacking.
Holmes 2020 [16]	MY	Statistical Machine Learning	Near-Infrared Hyperspectral Reflectance Imaging	<i>Cannabis sativa</i> (Flowers, Stems, Leaves)	Classification of different parts of the cannabis plant based on spectral data.	Statistical machine learning with hyperspectral imaging can effectively classify cannabis plant parts.	Data preprocessing steps, specific machine learning models used, and rigor of validation process need examination in the full text.
Chumchu 2023 [17]	TH	Not applicable (Dataset paper)	Image dataset	Cannabis seeds (17 classes)	Creation of a labeled image dataset for training machine learning models.	Provided a dataset of 3434 high-quality images of 17 cannabis seed classes.	Potential limitations in the representativeness of seed categories and standardization of image acquisition conditions.
Hendrick 2022 [18]	ID	Artificial Neural Network (ANN)	Portable Electronic Nose	Dry Cannabis	Classification of dry cannabis aroma using an ANN trained on sensor data.	ANN achieved 96% accuracy in predicting dry cannabis aroma.	Sensor array details, dataset creation for ANN training, model architecture, training process, and system validation need examination in the full text.
Kurnianingsih 2023 [19]	ID	Ensemble Learning (Soft Voting), ANFIS, Random Forest, MLP, k-NN, SVM	Electronic Nose (custom hardware)	Methamphetamine (in urine)	Combining outputs of multiple classifiers using soft voting to improve detection accuracy.	Proposed ensemble learning approach aimed to improve methamphetamine detection in urine.	Details regarding sample collection, electronic nose sensors, data acquisition protocol, and ensemble model validation require further examination.

Table 1: Key findings of the included studies (cont'd)

First Author & Year	Country	AI Tool/ Method	Analytical Technique	Drug/s Analyzed	How AI Was Leveraged	Key Findings	Limitations Identified
Ooi 2023 [20]	MY	Gaussian Process Regression, Least Angle Regression, CCA, EnCCA, PLS, RPLS, PLSFS	Near-Infrared Hyperspectral Imaging	Cannabidiolic Acid (CBDA) content in <i>Cannabis sativa</i> L.	Estimation of CBDA content using various machine learning regression techniques on spectral data.	Gaussian Process Regression performed best; PLSFS offered interpretability.	Experimental setup for HSI, reference CBDA measurements, specific ML model parameters, and validation procedures need examination in the full text.
Aryati 2019 [21]	ID	Machine Learning	Spectral Imaging	Marijuana Plants (<i>Cannabis sativa</i> L.)	Review of methods and techniques for cannabis plant identification.	Provided an overview of the field.	Lack of detail on the systematicity of the literature search and synthesis methods raises concerns about potential bias.
Wong 2023 [22]	SG	Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Balanced Random Forest (BRF)	Gas Chromatography -Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS)	Novel Psychoactive Substances (NPS) - cathinones, cannabinoids, phenethylamines, piperazines, tryptamines, fentanyl, and other unrelated compounds	Classification of unknown NPS based on GC-MS data.	Balanced Random Forest model achieved a macro-F1 score of ~0.9.	Model's ability to generalize to truly novel NPS with significantly different structures might require further investigation.
Ooi 2023 [23]	MY	Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA), Ensemble CCA (EnCCA), Partial Least Squares Regression (PLS), Regularized PLS (RPLS), PLS with Feature Selection (PLSFS)	Near-Infrared Hyperspectral Imaging	Tetrahydrocannabinolic Acid (THCA) concentration in <i>Cannabis sativa</i> L.	Estimation of THCA concentration using sparse and reproducible machine learning on spectral data.	PLSFS method led to reproducible models with small feature sets.	Lack of detailed information on sample selection, HSI data acquisition parameters, and specific quantitative results.

Note (country abbreviations): **ID** - Indonesia; **MY** - Malaysia; **SG** - Singapore; **TH** - Thailand.

Table 2: Critical appraisal of included studies

First Author & Year	Overall Risk of Bias	Key Strengths	Key Limitations
Chang 2025 [12]	Moderate	Rapid, nondestructive method; high accuracy; first application to Malaysian samples	Lack of detail on sample selection, data collection parameters, and validation methodology
Yusof 2021 [13]	High	Novel use of shallow 1DCNN with 3D molecular descriptors; hyperparameter optimization	Details of the dataset not fully clear; justification for the use of specific 3D molecular descriptors requires further scrutiny
Rahmantyo 2019 [14]	Moderate	Use of electronic tongue response analysis using SVM for cannabis samples - potential for portable detection.	Lack of access to the full text to determine critical methodological details regarding sample preparation, sensor characteristics, SVM model parameters, and validation procedures.

Table 2: Critical appraisal of included studies (Cont'd)

First Author & Year	Overall Risk of Bias	Key Strengths	Key Limitations
Aryati 2020 [15]	Moderate	Direct comparison of machine learning and deep learning methods with pharmacophore modeling for classifying cannabinoid- and cathinone-derived compounds.	High reported accuracies of deep learning models necessitate careful examination of the validation strategies employed and the potential for overfitting, especially given the complexity of these models and the potential size of the datasets used.
Holmes 2020 [16]	Moderate	Novel application of NIR hyperspectral imaging. High classification accuracy. Identification of important spectral bands. Nondestructive approach.	Limited sample size. Convenience sampling. Lack of direct chemical validation. Different imaging conditions.
Chumchu 2023 [17]	Low	Creation and public availability of a dedicated image dataset of cannabis seeds specifically designed for machine learning applications.	Potential limitations in the representativeness of the selected cannabis seed varieties and the standardization of image acquisition conditions (e.g., variations in lighting and angle) should be considered when utilizing this resource for training machine learning models.
Hendrick 2022 [18]	Moderate	Novel application of e-Nose technology. Development of a portable system. Use of ANN for data analysis.	Small sample size. Insufficient detail on sample characteristics. Limited discussion of confounding factors. Lack of comparison with other detection methods.
Kurnianingsih 2023 [19]	Moderate	Proposal of a novel ensemble learning approach using soft voting to enhance the accuracy of methamphetamine detection in urine.	Details regarding sample collection criteria and the representativeness of the samples are lacking. Specifics of the electronic nose sensors and data acquisition protocol are not provided. The validation methodology and detailed performance results for the ensemble model require further examination.
Ooi 2023 [20]	Moderate	Systematic evaluation of regression techniques. Use of robust reference method (LCMS). Detailed analysis of model performance. Demonstrates potential of hyperspectral imaging.	Relatively small sample size. Variability of CBDA within samples. Limited generalizability to high-THCA varieties.
Aryati 2019 [21]	High	Provides a review of the existing literature on the identification of marijuana plants (<i>Cannabis sativa</i> L.) using spectral imaging and machine learning techniques.	The lack of detailed information regarding the systematicity of the literature search strategy and the methods used for synthesizing the findings from the included studies raises significant concerns about potential bias in the comprehensiveness and objectivity of the review.
Wong 2023 [22]	Low	Development of machine learning models for screening unknown NPS utilizing only GC-MS data.	While the dataset includes a diverse selection of compounds, the model's ability to generalize to truly novel NPS with significantly different structures might require further investigation.

Table 2: Critical appraisal of included studies (Cont'd)

First Author & Year	Overall Risk of Bias	Key Strengths	Key Limitations
Ooi 2023 [23]	High	Focus on developing a sparse and reproducible machine learning technique using near-infrared hyperspectral imaging for the estimation of tetrahydrocannabinolic acid (THCA) concentration in <i>Cannabis sativa</i> L.	Lack of detailed information on sample selection, HSI data acquisition, and specific quantitative results on model performance and reproducibility in the available snippets.

4. Discussion

This scoping review identified and examined 12 studies that applied AI to the forensic chemical analysis of illicit drugs, Cannabis, and NPS in SEA. The studies varied widely in their methodological approaches, target substances, and technological platforms, reflecting the diverse and evolving landscape of AI applications in regional forensic science.

Several studies demonstrated the potential of ML and DL models to significantly improve the accuracy and efficiency of substance classification. Spectroscopic techniques such as ATR-FTIR and near-infrared hyperspectral imaging were frequently coupled with supervised learning algorithms like RF, SVM, and sparse alternating decision trees, achieving high classification accuracies (often exceeding 95%). These models were applied to methamphetamine, Cannabis components, CBDA/THCA quantification, and NPS categorization. Ensemble methods and regression models further expanded AI’s utility for quantifying drug content and interpreting spectral or sensor-based data.

Studies involving E-tongue and E-nose technologies, combined with ML, illustrated the feasibility of portable, real-time detection systems for Cannabis and methamphetamine, thereby providing viable alternatives to traditional methods such as GC-MS and LC-MS. Meanwhile, dataset-centric studies introduced standardized image repositories for Cannabis seeds, supporting future AI research.

Despite these promising developments, common limitations emerged. Many studies were constrained by small or region-specific datasets, with limited sample diversity and insufficient detail on sampling methods, increasing the risk of selection bias. Several lacked robust validation procedures or did not fully report metrics such as precision, recall, and cross-validation strategies, raising concerns about overfitting and generalizability. Moreover, few studies addressed the operational integration of AI tools into real-world forensic workflows, limiting their immediate applicability across laboratories with varying levels of technical capacity.

Collectively, these findings suggest that AI holds great promise for transforming forensic chemical analysis in Southeast Asia. However, substantial work remains to overcome methodological, infrastructural, and standardization barriers.

5. Proposed Roadmap for Leveraging AI Tools for Illicit Drug, Cannabis, and NPS Analyses in SEA

To fully realize AI’s transformative potential in forensic chemical analysis, the following recommendations are proposed.

Phase 1: Standardize Data Collection and Validation Protocols

Uniform methodologies for sample collection, data acquisition, and cross-validation should be established to improve reproducibility and facilitate model comparison.

Phase 2: Develop Regional Data Repositories

Creating open-access, diverse datasets—spanning various drug types, formulations, and analytical techniques—will enhance model generalizability and support cross-border collaboration.

Phase 3: Promote Interdisciplinary and Cross-Laboratory Collaborations

Collaboration between forensic scientists, data scientists, and regulatory bodies is essential to design AI systems that are technically robust and contextually appropriate for SEA forensic laboratories.

Phase 4: Invest in Capacity Building and Infrastructure

Training programs, funding for instrumentation, and institutional support are needed to bridge the gap between research and practice, especially in low-resource settings.

Phase 5: Establish Ethical and Regulatory Frameworks

Guidelines should be developed to ensure ethical deployment, data privacy, and legal admissibility of AI-generated forensic results.

Figure 3: Roadmap for Leveraging AI Tools for Illicit Drug, Cannabis, and NPS Analyses in SEA

5. Conclusion

This review highlights the emerging but uneven application of AI tools for forensic chemical analysis in SEA. The reviewed studies showcase significant potential for enhancing analytical accuracy, reducing processing times, and enabling portable, nondestructive testing for various controlled substances. However, the current landscape is marked by fragmented efforts, varying methodological rigor, and a lack of standardized practices.

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